

USE OF LOW POTENTIAL SECONDARY HEAT ENERGY RESOURCES.

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the ways and conditions of use of low-potential secondary thermal energy resources (IIER). Methods of effective use of IIER are proposed.*

Keywords: *IIER-Secondary beverage energy resources, heat carrier, intermediate heat carrier, potential, regenerative circulating heat exchanger, heat flow, heat pipes, hot layer.*

Аннотация *Мақолада наст потенциалли иккиламчи иссиқлик энергия ресурсларидан (ИИЭР) фойдаланиши йўллари ва ҳолати тахлил қилинган. ИИЭРдан самарали фойдаланиши усуллари тақлиф этилган.*

Калит сўзлар: *ИИЭР-Иккиламчи иччиқлик энергияси ресурслари, иссиқлик ташувчи, оралиқ иссиқлик ташувчи, потенциал, регенератив айланувчи иссиқлик алмашувчи аппарати, иссиқлик оқими, иссивлик трубалари, қайнар қатлам.*

MAIN PART

The peculiarity of the ventilation system is that the heat of the heated air supplied to the production building (including public buildings) is expelled with the air of the suction system without being used.

According to the data, the amount of heat used for heating and air exchange systems of industrial buildings is 36 million tons of conditional fuel per year. In the near future, it can reach 47 mln. tons of conventional fuel per year. Therefore, the use of heat recovery devices in the air exchange systems of industrial enterprises allows to use a significant amount of the heat of the outgoing air and, as a result, to achieve energy savings.

Today, the following ways of using the secondary heat of the exhaust air have been chosen as a feasible solution from a real technical and economic point of view:

- use of heat disposal devices with an intermediate heat carrier (heat pipes, a layer of dispersed particles or a hot layer are used as an intermediate heat carrier);
- Using a conventional air heater as a heat exchange device;
- use of heating sections of air conditioners produced in series in our industry;
- use of air-type regenerative rotating heat exchangers as a disposal system.

However, studies show that the utilization rate of low-potential secondary heat energy is very low. The reason for this is that the production of "heat pipes" has not been established in our industry, the efficiency of rotating regenerative heat exchange devices is low, and there are cases where both flows merge into each other.

The use of special materials as intermediate heat carriers of rotating regenerative air heaters can increase the efficiency of the device:

In particular: some metals and metal alloys absorb heat and change shape when heated.

When it cools, it gives off the heat it has absorbed and returns to its original form.

Use of material and material mixture with very high mass heat capacity as intermediate heat transfer material.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the use of materials as an intermediate heat carrier allows to improve the performance of the device. Even in the ranges of very small temperature differences ($\Delta t=10\div 150^{\circ}\text{C}$) of the main heat carriers, it enables effective use of existing heat flow.

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